

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A571

18 August 1997

TACIA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A571

DATE: 18/8/97

Take off :

Landing :

Aircraft Scientist : A KATE
Flight Leader : I. PURE
Others : LD : M. PICKERING
OZIE : K. DUNN
EGLL : T. KENT
LUTON : B. GARDNER
NOXY : S. BAGGITT
PENRICE : B. BARRY
FORMALDEHYDE : G. WILLS
CO : S. SCHWITGEN
PERCA : T. GILSON

Captain : M. PURE
Co-pilot : C. O'BRIEN
Navigator : T. SIMPSON
Engineer : M. LENNARDS
Loadmaster : K. CROSS

MISSION SCIENTISTS

+ SF20 : DEITER KLEY
PAUL MONKS
CLAIRE REEVES

Trials Instructions : MIF1 TACIA :
Operating area : NORTH SEA

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A571 18-AUG-97 10:18:30-17:03:30GMT

INS TRACK - run

A571 18-AUG-97 Height time series

A571, 18th August, 1997
TACIA
Southern North Sea

Start time	End time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
101810					Take off RAF Lyneham
103441	105500	R1	FL100	070°	
110801	111859	P1	FL100 250'	090°	
112540	112920	R2.1	350'	070°	
112920	114914	P2	400' 5000'	070°	Runs 2.2-2.4 within P2
113024	113252	R2.2	1000'	070°	
113534	113737	R2.3	3000'	065°	
114413	114814	R2.4	4000'	250°	
114914	115344	R2.5	5000'		
115759	121633	P3	5000' 400'	070°	Runs 3.1-3.3 within P3
115856	120551	R3.1	4000'	070°	
120618	120940	R3.2	3000'	070°	
121225	121519	R3.3	1000'	070°	
121633	121934	R4.1	400'	070°	
121934	123315	P4	400' 5000'	070°	Runs 4.2-4.4 within P4
122005	122332	R4.2	1000'	070°	
122636	122855	R4.3	3500'	070°	
122921	123220	R4.4	4000'	070°	
123315	123850	R4.5	5000'	075°	
123850	125237	P5	5000' 50'	070°	Runs 5.1-5.3 within P5
123943	124210	R5.1	4000'	070°	
124236	124502	R5.2	3500'	070°	
124817	125050	R5.3	1000'	075°	
125335	125615	R5.4	100'	070°	
131207	131847	P6	5200' 50'	250°	
131847	133550	P7	50' 5200'	255°	Runs 7.1-7.4 within P7
131917	132244	R7.1	100'	240°	
132426	132650	R7.2	1000'	250°	
132953	133131	R7.3	3500'	255°	
133201	133445	R7.4	4000'	255°	
133550	134012	R7.5	5200'	250°	
134012	135150	P8	5200' 50'	245°	Runs 8.1-8.3 within P8
134122	134258	R8.1	4000'	250°	
134325	134518	R8.2	3500'	250°	
134833	134941	R8.3	1000'	250°	
135150	141214	P9	50' 5300'	230°	Runs 9.1-9.4 within P9
135208	135307	R9.1	100'	250°	
135442	135618	R9.2	1000'	240°	
135921	140055	R9.3	3500'	230°	
140121	141058	R9.4	4000'	230°	
141214	141655	R9.5	5300'	260°	
144135	144311	R10.1	5300'	070°	
144311	145513	P10	5300' 50'	070°	Runs 10.2-10.4 within P10
144445	144613	R10.2	4000'	070°	
144755	144906	R10.3	2500'	070°	
145152	145307	R10.4	1000'	075°	
145513	151025	P11	50' 5300'	060°	Runs 11.1-11.4 within P11
145522	145629	R11.1	100'	060°	
145850	150012	R11.2	1000'	060°	
150200	150400	R11.3	2500'	060°	
150732	150900	R11.4	4000'	060°	
151025	151222	R11.5	5300'	070°	
151222	152737	P12	5300' 50'	070°	Runs 12.1-12.3 within P12
151352	151652	R12.1	4000'	070°	
151832	151952	R12.2	2500'	070°	
152207	152514	R12.3	1000'	070°	

152737	154159	P13	50'	5300'	070°	Runs 13.1-13.4 within P13
152745	153151	R13.1	100'		070°	
153342	153500	R13.2	1000'		070°	
153654	153753	R13.3	2500'		070°	
153924	154042	R13.4	4000'		070°	
154159	154353	R13.5	5300'		070°	
155740	155914	R14.1	5300'		250°	
155914	161121	P14	5300'	50'	250°	Runs 14.2-14.4 within P14
160045	160215	R14.2	4000'		250°	
160347	160506	R14.3	2500'		250°	
160738	160903	R14.4	1000'		250°	
161121	162303	P15	50'	5300'	250°	Runs 15.1-15.4 within P15
161128	161235	R15.1	100'		250°	
161412	161526	R15.2	1000'		250°	
161731	161842	R15.3	2500'		250°	
162017	162144	R15.4	4000'		250°	
162303	162710	R15.5	5300'		250°	
162710	163853	P16	5300'	50'	250°	Runs 16.1-16.3 within P16
162840	163000	R16.1	4000'		250°	
163133	163244	R16.2	2500'		250°	
163501	163645	R16.3	1000'		250°	
163853	170335	P17	50'	FL110	240°	Runs 17.1-17.6 within P17
163904	164017	R17.1	100'		240°	
164159	164330	R17.2	1000'		240°	
164553	164708	R17.3	2500'		240°	
164840	164958	R17.4	4000'		240°	
165117	165310	R17.5	5300'		240°	
165342	155805	R17.6	5800'		255°	
170335	172323	R18	FL110		255°	

175702

Land at RAF Lyneham

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#####1 125800 131016 R1 3000'
0 131016 131345 P1 3000'-FL050
1 131345 132232 R2 FL050
0 132232 133220 P2 FL050-FL150
1 132220 135216 R3 FL150
0 135421 141058 P3 FL150-500'
1 141124 142620 R4 800'-1100'
0 142711 145338 P4 1100'-FL270
1 145507 151156 R5 FL270
0 151304 152507 P5 FL270-FL150
1 152507 154150 R6 FL150

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TACIA August 1997

Flight A571

18 August 1997

OBJECTIVE: To measure chemical composition of polluted plume at different distanced from land.

LOCATION: Southeastern North Sea.

WEATHER: Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation where possible.

SAMPLING PATTERN:

- 1] Take-off Lyneham 11:00 local time.
- 2] Ascend to 3000ft and hold for 5 minutes for chemical instrumentation.
- 3] Transit to sampling area as convenient. **(FLIGHT LEVEL 100)**
- 4] 15 minute straight and level run for NOxy Calibration.
- 5] Profile from transit altitude to 50 ft. (Or minimum safe altitude)
- 6] Sawtooth and bottle sampling pattern as shown in diagrams, approximately perpendicular to the wind.
- 7] 15 minute straight and level run for NOxy Calibration.
- 8] Return to Lyneham as convenient.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS: Constant cabin pressure on level runs.
Communications with TACIA Ops required (SATCOM or Phone patch).

AIRCRAFT FLYING PROGRAMME

DATE 16 August 1997

FLIGHT NO A571

FTI MRF1 TACIA

Aircraft scientist	A Kaye	NOxy	S Bauguitte
Flight leader	I Rule	Peroxide	B Bandy
Cloud physics	M Pickering	Formaldehyde	G Mills
CCN/PSAP/Oz	K Dewey	CO	S Schmitgen
Pan ECGC	J Kent	PERCA	T Green
Bottles	J Pantrey	Project Scientists	X 3

Pre-flight clearance M Pickering / ~~J Pantrey~~ dep 0700

B. GARDNER

B. GARDNER

FTOs Depart F'boro 0720

Briefing 0830 Take off 1030 Land at 1830
Lynham

Press RETURN for next display (H for help)

NEXT DAY 15-AUG-1997 12:44

+ DEITER KEY
PAN MARKS
CLAIRE REVIEWS

14 SCIENTISTS + 5 A/C = 19

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 4571

Date: 18/8/97

A/S Name: A. KATE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for *SEVERAL*
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period *INDEF*
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project *TRACIA*
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? *INDEF*
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight A571 — TACIA Monday, 18 August 1997

Aircraft Scientist Debrief:

The meteorological conditions were dominated by a high pressure cell over Scandinavia and a series of frontal systems approaching in the North Atlantic. The winds in the North Sea were generally slack with a gentle outflow from continental Europe.

The Aircraft Scientist display was not functioning properly, which limited the information available on the flight deck. HORACE locked up halfway through the flight and had to be rebooted. After the restart the A/S display functioned properly, although the Omega Lat/Long read 0,0 through out most of the flight.

The sortie brief was executed to plan with the exception of an additional profile on the first track just north of the German coast. During the flight 64 bottles were filled for later analysis. The mission scientists were very pleased with the flight and it appears to have been a very successful TACIA sortie.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A571

Date: 18/8/97

User: A. KATE/H. RICHER

Interactive by: I. RUIE

Date: 19/8/17

Renav

KALWAN FILTERING

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = - 0.2334E+1

b = + 0.3604E-2

c = + 0.2448E-6

LWC

VERY LITTLE CLOUD ENCOUNTERED IN FLIGHT - OCCASIONALLY
CLIPPED THE TOPS OF CU.

Heimann / Barnes

ML

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A571 Date: 18/8/97 Page...!...of

CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854	✓		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	0000		F/S O/S TORQUE 4.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1522		F/S O/S TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000	✓		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3863	350	✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3299	1002	✓		
	A/S	9	0000	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0390	90			
	UP2S	82	0242	20			
	UIRS	83	0201		↓ NO ₂		
	UP1Z	84	0151	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	0768	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	0210		↓ NO ₂	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2356	} 21		As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2370			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0200		↓ NO ₂	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0171	-15			
	LP2S	92	0131	-10			
	LIRS	93	0024		↓ NO ₂		
	LP1Z	94	0101	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	0152	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0231		↓ NO ₂	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2395	} 21		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2357			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0200		↓ NO ₂	As IAT	
	J/W	42	0906			As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	3253	24			
	HYCC	59	0717	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	2457	18		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0552				
	DTF	10	1550	21			
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	1042	21		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	2501	✓			
	HEIM	141	2650				
	PRTC	142	2383	✓		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	3469	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	0702	✓		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0222				
	O3P	106	2030			P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145m.B	
	O3RG	113	1294				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	571			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0083			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0877			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	8			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3705	3856 1452	3705	0473	5704	3681	3703	0745 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	1220			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 8

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	3454	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1202	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0201	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2562	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2262	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2077	} STABLE ✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2119			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1026			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2042				
	EV2V	171	2045				
	NPWR	172	3355				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	5468				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon ✓		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon ✓		

Flight Leader's Pre (In)-Flight Check List

Flight No: A571

Date: 18/8/97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2854				Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1899	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	0729	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	6095	75000			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2697	98k			As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3226	072	✓	971 ✓	
	A/S	9	1353	150			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	2268	760	✓		
	UP2S	82	1902	752	✓		
	UIRS	83	0875			JNO ₂	
	UP1Z	84	0155	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0148	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0879			JNO ₂	Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2659	7			As IAT
	UP2T	88	2620	7			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0200			JNO ₂	As IAT
	LP1S	91	0598	157			
	LP2S	92	0542	150			
	LIRS	93	0203			JNO ₂	
	LP1Z	94	0150	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0153	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0650			SNO ₂	Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2698	7			As IAT
	LP2T	98	2600	7			As IAT
	LIRT	99	0200			JNO ₂	As IAT
	J/W	42	1207	0.0			As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	2232	7.0			
	HYCC	59	0770	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	1792	-11			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0608				
	DTF	10	2265	7			
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	2602	7			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	2572				
	HEIM	141	2686				
	PRTC	142	3064	??			approx 2380
	TWCD	70	1209	✓			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	6091	✓			0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	036				
	O3P	106	1588				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	2171				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	571			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0710			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0804			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0011			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3161	2856 1572	3164	0800	3177	3724	3179	0760 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	0598	52		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0021	2		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: ↓

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	1529			0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2602			2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1205			0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2803			2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2272			2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2709			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1065			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	6023			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	2489				
	EV2V	171	3158				
	NPWR	172	2659				
	EVIC	173	4007				
	EV2C	174	6007				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A ...571.....

Date ...18/8/97.....

Page ...1..... of ...5.....

Video Tape	
No. A571#1	Ends 1432
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51 30.40N	51 30.40N
Long	001 54.18W	001 54.20W
Time	0818	0819
Status	S3	← ALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ n

ON PAN (1) LYNEHAM

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
074812				DATA ON					
095700				SET INU TO NAV					
101810				TO LYNEHAM					
				START RUN					
103441	9	FL100		070	180	4.8	-16	OFF	
				END RUN					
105500	10	FL100		070 180	1.8		-2	OFF	
				START PROFILE 1			↓		
110801	11	FL100		090	180				
				END P1					
111854	13	250	1012						SS=1
				START RUN		2.1			
112540	14	350		070					
				END RUN		2.1 / START PROFILE 2	↗		
112920	15	400							
				START RUN		2.2			
113024	16	1000		070	190				X 113200(17) START VIDEO
				RESTART P2 / END RUN		2.2			
113252	18	1000		070					
				INTERUPT P2 / START RUN		2.3			
113534	20	3000		065					
				END RUN		2.3			(P2 STILL INTERRUPTED)
115737	21	3000							

Video Tape	
No.	A571 #1
Ends	1432
<u>(C)</u> / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	53 03.60N	53 04.93N
Long	003 06.60E	003 04.08E
Time	1147	1148
Status	S's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	<u>(y)</u> / n
HORACE recording to disc	<u>(y)</u> / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	<u>(y)</u> / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
			RESTART P2						
11435	22	3000		250	128	17.2			
			INTERCPT P2 / START RUN 2.4						
11445	23	4000							
			END RUN 2.4 / RESTART P2						
11474	24	4000							
			(END) INTERCPT P2 / START RUN 2.5						
11494	25	5000							
			END RUN 2.5						
115344	26	5000							
			START PROFILE 3				↓		
115759	27	5000							
			INTERCPT P3 / START RUN 3.1						
115836	28	4000		070	175				
			RESTART P3 / END RUN 3.1						
120521	29	4000		070					
			INTERCPT P3 / START RUN 3.2						
120618	30	3000		070					
			END RUN 3.2 / RESTART P3						
120640	31	3000							
			INTERCPT P3 / START RUN 3.3						
121225	33	1000		070					
			END RUN 3.3 / RESTART P3						
121579	34	1000		070					
			END P3 / START P3 RUN 4.1						
121633	35	400	1022						SS=1
			END RUN 4.1 / START PROFILE 4						
121984	36	600		070					
			INTERCPT P4 / START RUN 4.2						
122005	37	1000		070					
			END RUN 4.2 / RESTART P4						
122332	38	1000							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 571.....

Date 12/8/17.....

Page 2 of 5.....

Video Tape	
No. <u>A571#1</u>	
Ends <u>1432</u>	
<u>FFC</u> / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			INTERDUPT P4 / START RUN 4.3						
122636	40	3500		070					
			END RUN 4.3 / RESUME P4						
122835	41	3500							
			INTERDUPT P4 / START RUN 4.4						
122921	42	4000		070					
			END RUN 4.4 / RESUME P4						
123220	43	4000		070					
			INTERDUPT P4 / START RUN 4.5						
123315	44	3000		075					
			END RUN 4.5 / START PROFILE 5						
123850	45	5000							
			INTERDUPT P5 / START RUN 5.1						
123943	46	4000							
			END RUN 5.1 / RESUME P5						
124210	47	4000							
			INTERDUPT P5 / START RUN 5.2						
124236	48	3500		070					
			END RUN 5.2 / RESUME P5						
124502	49	3500							
			INTERDUPT P5 / START RUN 5.3						
124817	51	1000		075					
			END RUN 5.3 / RESUME P5						
125050	52	1000							
			END P5 / START RUN 5.4						
125237	53	50'							
			INTERDUPT P6 / START RUN 5.4						
125335	54	100'		102					
			END RUN 5.4 / RESUME P6						
125615	55	100'							

Video Tape	
No.	A571#1
Ends	1432
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	54 55.93N	54 59.41N
Long	007 57.38E	007 55.51E
Time	1306	1250
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) n

. GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
131207	56	5200'	250	250					
131847	58	50'							
131917	59	100'		240					
132244	60	100'		250					
132426	61	10250		250	185				
132650	62	10250							
132953	64	3800		255	185				
133131	65	3800							
133207	66	4050		255					
133445	67	4080		255					
133550	68	5200		250					
134012	69	5200		245					
134122	70	4000		250					
134258	71	4080							
134325	72	3500							
134510	73	3500		250	180				
134833	75	1000		250					

VILLIENS INN
WYBOURGTON

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No **A 571**.....

Date **18/8/97**.....

Page **3** of **5**

Video Tape
No. A571#1
Ends 1432 (1720)
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE ☒ y/n
HORACE recording to disc ☒ y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports ☒ y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
13444	76	1000							
			END RUN 8.3 / RESUME P8						
135150	77	50'	1022						SS=1
			END PT / START P9						
135208	78	100'		250					
			INTERUPT P9 / START RUN 9.1						
135307	79	100'							
			END RUN 9.1 / RESUME P9						
135442	80	1000		240					
			INTERUPT P9 / START RUN 9.2						
135615	81	1000'		230					
			END RUN 9.2 / RESUME P9						
135824	82	3500		230					
			INTERUPT P9 / START RUN 9.3						
140055	84	3500							
			END RUN 9.3 / RESUME P9						
140121	85	4000'							
			INTERUPT P9 / START RUN 9.4						
14058	86	4000		230					
			END RUN 9.4 / RESUME P9						
141214	87	5300		260					
			INTERUPT P9 / START RUN 9.5						
141655	88	5300							
			END RUN 9.5 / START P9.5						
142545	89		END VIDEO A571#1 COUNT = 5244						
142623	90		START VIDEO A571#2 COUNT = 0000						
			START ENGINE RUN 10.1						
144435	91	5300		070					

Video Tape	
No.	ASTR#2
Ends	1720
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
144311	92	3300							
			END RUN 10.1 / START P10 ↓						
144445	93	4000							
			INTERUPT P10 / START RUN 10.2						
144613	94	4100		070					
			END RUN 10.2 / RESTART P10						
144755	95	2500		070					
			INTERUPT P10 / START RUN 10.3						
144906	96	2500		070					
			END RUN 10.3 / RESTART P10 ↓						
145152	98	1000		075					
			INTERUPT P10 / START RUN 10.4						
145307	99	1000							
			END RUN 10.4 / RESTART P10						
145513	100	50'							
			END P10 / START P11 ↗						
145522	101	100'							
			INTERUPT P11 / START RUN 11.1						
145624	102	100'		060					
			END RUN 11.1 / RESTART P11						
145850	103	1000		060					
			INTERUPT P11 / START RUN 11.2						
150012	104	1000							
			END RUN 11.2 / RESTART P11						
150200	106	2500							
			INTERUPT P11 / START RUN 11.3						
150600	107	2500		060					
			END RUN 11.3 / RESTART P11						
150732	108	4000							
			INTERUPT P11 / START RUN 11.4						
150900	109	4000							
			END RUN 11.4 / RESTART P11						
151025	110	5300		070					
			INTERUPT P11 / START RUN 11.5						

Research Flight

1820Z ETA

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No **A 571**.....

Date **18/8/97**.....

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Video Tape	
No. A571 #2	
Ends 1720	
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / n
HORACE recording to disc	y / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
							END RUN 11.5 / START PROFILE P12 ↓		
151222	111	5300		070			INTERLUPT P12 / START RUN 12.1		
151352	112	4000'		070			END RUN 12.1 / RESTART P12		
151652	115	4000					INTERLUPT P12 / START RUN 12.2		
151832	114	2500		070			END RUN 12.2 / RESTART P12		
151952	115	2500		070			INTERLUPT P12 / START RUN 12.3		
152207	117	1000		070			END RUN 12.3 / RESTART P12		
152514	118	1000					END P12 / START P13		
152757	119	50'		1022			INTERLUPT P13 / START RUN 13.1		1
152745	120	100'					END RUN 13.1 / RESTART P13		
153157	121	100'					INTERLUPT P13 / START RUN 13.2		
153342	122	1000		070			END RUN 13.2 / RESTART P13		
153500	123	1000		070			INTERLUPT P13 / START RUN 13.3		
153654	124	2500		070			END RUN 13.3 / RESTART P13		
153753	125	2500					INTERLUPT P13 / START RUN 13.4		
153924	126	1000		070					

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A AS71
 Project TACIA Date 18/8/97
 Tape No AS71#2 User A. KATE Retention Period INDEF

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
142623	0000	FFC	START RECORDING
1726	?	FFC	END OF TAPE

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A 571**.....

Project **TACIA**.....

Date **12/8/97**.....

Tape No **A571#1** User **A:KATE**.....

Retention Period **INDEX**.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
113200	0200	FFC	START RECORDING
142545	5894	FFC	END TAPE

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <i>AS71</i>					Operator: <i>COSS</i>					Date: <i>18/8/97</i>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = <i>8</i>					Optimisation = <i>8</i>				Optimisation = <i>8</i>				
			Back Flush = <i>42</i>					Back Flush = <i>42</i>				Back Flush = <i>40</i>				
			Flow rate = <i>40</i>					Flow rate = <i>42</i>				Flow rate = <i>41</i>				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
					<i>387</i>	<i>1076</i>				<i>30.7</i>	<i>1125</i>			<i>28.5</i>	<i>1164</i>	
<i>#1</i>	<i>112200</i>	<i>300'</i>	<i>521</i>	<i>603</i>				<i>494</i>	<i>693</i>			<i>472</i>	<i>-72</i>			<i>R2.1</i>
<i>#2</i>	<i>113045</i>	<i>1000</i>	<i>520</i>	<i>592</i>				<i>495</i>	<i>682</i>			<i>469</i>	<i>-72</i>			<i>R2.2</i>
<i>#3</i>	<i>113610</i>	<i>3000'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>546</i>				<i>493</i>	<i>628</i>			<i>467</i>	<i>-67</i>			<i>R2.3</i>
<i>#4</i>	<i>114435</i>	<i>4000'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>526</i>				<i>489</i>	<i>606</i>			<i>465</i>	<i>-68</i>			<i>R2.4</i>
<i>#5</i>	<i>114915</i>	<i>5000'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>510</i>				<i>486</i>	<i>583</i>			<i>463</i>	<i>-68</i>			<i>R2.5</i>
<i>#6</i>	<i>115957</i>	<i>4000'</i>	<i>521</i>	<i>527</i>				<i>486</i>	<i>607</i>			<i>461</i>	<i>-69</i>			<i>R3.1</i>
<i>#7</i>	<i>120614</i>	<i>3000'</i>	<i>520</i>	<i>549</i>				<i>484</i>	<i>633</i>			<i>459</i>	<i>-72</i>			<i>R3.2</i>
<i>#8</i>	<i>121239</i>	<i>1000'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>592</i>				<i>483</i>	<i>685</i>			<i>456</i>	<i>-68</i>			<i>R3.3</i>
<i>#9</i>	<i>121740</i>	<i>550'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>594</i>				<i>487</i>	<i>691</i>			<i>457</i>	<i>-68</i>			<i>R4.1</i>
<i>#10</i>	<i>122650</i>	<i>3500'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>538</i>				<i>480</i>	<i>622</i>			<i>456</i>	<i>-69</i>			<i>R4.3</i>
<i>#11</i>	<i>123330</i>	<i>5000'</i>	<i>511</i>	<i>511</i>				<i>480</i>	<i>588</i>			<i>457</i>	<i>-68</i>			<i>R4.4</i>
<i>#12</i>	<i>125530</i>	<i>100'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>697</i>				<i>471</i>	<i>766</i>			<i>456</i>	<i>-69</i>			<i>R5.4</i>

Negative peaks in

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>AST1</u>					Operator: <u>Doss</u>					Date: <u>18/8/97</u>				
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments	
			Optimisation = <u>4</u>					Optimisation = <u>8</u>				Optimisation = <u>8</u>					
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =					
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =					
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP					
#13	131925	100'	520	607					481	706			458	-74			127.1
#14	132434	1000'	520	550					481	688			458	-71			127.2
#15	132800	3500'	520	526					481	623			458	-72			127.3
#16	133615	5200'	520	507					481	581			456	-66			127.5
#17	134335	3500'	519	536					482	622			459	-70			128.2
#18	135215	100'	520	607					482	706			459	-69			129.1
#19	135930	3500'	520	551					481	619			458	-69			129.3
#20	141214	5200'	520	501					481	577			457	-67			129.5
#20	141940	5200'	518	513					477	589			454	-7			130.1
#22	144430	4000'	519	524					475	605			451	-68			140.2
#22	145152	4000'	519	581					474	683			451	-70			140.4
#23	14950	1000'	519	589					473	686			459	-71			141.2
#24	151843	2500'	519	586					474	646			459	-70			142.2

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <i>AS71</i>					Operator: <i>JSS</i>					Date: <i>18/8/97</i>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation =					Optimisation =				Optimisation =				
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =				
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
<i>#15</i>	<i>152610</i>	<i>100'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>609</i>				<i>472</i>	<i>712</i>			<i>449</i>	<i>74</i>			<i>R13.1</i>
<i>#16</i>	<i>153715</i>	<i>2500'</i>	<i>519</i>	<i>558</i>				<i>472</i>	<i>648</i>			<i>449</i>	<i>-71</i>			<i>R13.3</i>
<i>#17</i>	<i>154300</i>	<i>5300'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>503</i>				<i>472</i>	<i>560</i>			<i>440</i>	<i>-73</i>			
<i>#18</i>	<i>158758</i>	<i>5300'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>501</i>				<i>470</i>	<i>560</i>			<i>447</i>	<i>-72</i>			<i>R14.1</i>
<i>#19</i>	<i>160412</i>	<i>2500'</i>	<i>518</i>	<i>558</i>				<i>465</i>	<i>645</i>			<i>447</i>	<i>-79</i>			<i>R14.3</i>

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

 Flight No. AS71

 Date 10/8

 Sheet no. 1/6

Sample No.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
1	R13		↙	400'	112645	112850	112857	2.5	RUN 2.1
2	R28 R13		↗	1000	113030	113230	113245	"	2.2
3	R13		↗	3000	113540	113740	113750	"	2.3
4	R9		↗	4000	114420	114620	114630	"	2.4
5	R42		↗	5000	114924 114924	115125	115132	"	2.5
6	R32		↘	4000	115856	120100	120125	"	3.01
7	R38		↘	3000	120618 120618	120820	120835	"	3.2
8	R25		↘	1000	121225	121428	121440	"	3.3
9	R14 R4		↘	RAD 550'	121715	121915	121925		4.01
10	R23		↗	1000	122030	122230	122240		4.02
11	R4		↗	3500	122638	112840	112850		4.3
12	R5		↗	4000	122945	123148	113200		4.4

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. A571

Date 18/8/97

Sheet no. 2/6

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
13	R37		↗	5000	123315	123520	123535	2.5	4.5
14	R29		↘	4000	123943	124145	124200		5.1
15	R26		↘	3500	124240	124440	124455		5.2
16	R6		↘	1000	124818	125020	125040		5.3
7	R30		↘	100	125337	125540	125550		WAS 4?
18	N R 615			100	131917	132220	132230	2.5	<u>NILU BOTTLES</u> 7.1
19	N 306		↗	1000	132425	132630	132640	'	7.2
20	S07		↗	3500	132955	133120	133130	'	7.3
21	N 25.I		↗	4000	1332	133430	133440	4	7.4
22	N 16		↗	5200	133500	133650	133700	'	7.5
23	N 500		↘	4000	134122	134240	134250	'	8.1
24	N 7		↘	3500	134325	134450	134500		8.2

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. **AS71** Date **18/8/97** Sheet no. **3/6**

Sample No.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
5	N 328		↓	1000'	134833	134940	134980	2.5	8.3
6	N 308		↓	100'	135208	135250	135300	'	9.1
7	N 308 336		↗	1000'	135442	135530	135542	'	9.2
8	N 531		↗	3500'	135921	140030	140040	'	9.3
9	N 613		↗	4000'	140110	140235	140248	'	9.4
30	N 501		↗	5300'	141215	141255	141315	"	9.5
31	N 901		→	5300'	144135	144250	144300	"	10.1
32	N 311		↘	4000'	144445	144555	144605	"	10.2
33	N 4		↘	2500'	144755	144840	144858	"	10.3
34	N 614		↘	1000'	145152	145250	145300	"	10.4
35	N 503		↘	100'	145522	145610	145627	"	10.5 11.01
36	N 506		↗	1000'	1458	145955	150005		11.2

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. AS71 Date 18/8/97 Sheet no. 4/6

Sample No.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
37	N 505		↗	2500'	150200	150258	150305	205	11.3
38	N 191		↗	4000'	150732	150848	150855	"	11.4
39	N 315		↗	5300'	151010	151125	151140	"	11.5
40	N 105		↘	4000'	151352	151510	151525		12.1
41	N 302		↘	2500'	151832	151925	151945		12.2
42	N 61		↘	1000'	152207	152255	152310		12.3
43	N 60		↘	100'	152745	152845	152855		12.4 13.0
44	N 322		↗	1000'	153342 153342	153445	153455		13.2
45	N 314		↗	2500'	153634	153730	153745		13.3
46	N 81		↗	4000'	153924	154025	154035		13.4
47	N A06		↗	5300'	154159	154315	154325		13.5
48	N 681		↗	5300'	15574	155840	155855		14.0

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 4571 Date 18/8/97 Sheet no 5/6

Sample No.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
49	N 9I		↘	4000	1601	160150	160205	2.5	14.2
50	N 314		↘	2500'	1604	160445	160455	"	14.3
51	N 5I		↘	1000'	1608	160845	160855	"	14.4
52	N 34I		↘	100'	161128	161200	161220	"	15.1
53	N 17I		↗	1000	161412	161500	161518	"	15.2
54	N 318		↗	2500'	161731	161825	161838	"	15.3
55	N 327		↗	4000	162017	162105	162125	"	15.4
56	N 100		↗	5300'	162303	162400	162415		15.5
57	N 324		↘	4000'	162840	162945	162955		16.1
58	N 325		↘	2500	163133	163225	163238		16.2
59	N 57		↘	1000'	163501	163625	163640		16.3
60	N 40I		↘	100'	163904	163950	164010		17.1

CLOUD METRICS LOG

Flight No. A571

Date: 18/8/97

Operator: *mf*

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G.M.T. ORS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R.	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
123131												end of Run
133200	1140	0.11										Start Run 7.4 @ 4000'
133340	1025	0.11										
133415												end of Run
133534	670	0.12										5000'
133544												Start Run 7.5 @ 5200'
133600	830	0.12										
133800	440	0.12										
134013												end of Run Start 18
134100												Start Run 8.1 @ 4000'
134200	1150	0.13										
134300												end of Run
134335												Start Run 8.2 @ 3500'
134400	600	0.10										
134519												end of Run
134533												Start Run 8.3 @ 1000'
134900	1200	0.11	0.2	5								
134941												end of Run
135005												Start Run 8.4 @ 100'
135300	970	0.11	0.2	5								
135307												end of Run
135432												Start Run 9.2 @ 1000'
135500	1070	0.11										
135616												end of Run
135921												Start Run 9.3 @ 3500
140000	260	0.11										
140053												end of Run
140121												Start Run 9.4 @ 4000'
140200	80	0.09										
14055												end of Run
141214												Start Run 9.5 @ 5300
141300	30	0.09										
141500	50	0.08										
141700												end of Run
142135												Start Run 10.1 @ 5300'

CLOUD PHASIS LOG

Flight No. A571

Date: 18/1/97

Operator: MF

Page 7 of 8

I.M.T. IS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
61126	780	0.11	0.02	5								Start Run 15.1 @ 100'
61200	710	0.11										end of Run
61238												Start Run 15.2 @ 1000'
61413												end of Run
61500	650	0.11										Start Run 15.3 @ 2500'
61586												end of Run
61731												Start Run 15.4 @ 4000'
61800	745	0.12										end of Run
61845												Start Run 15.4 @ 4000'
62016												end of Run
62100	470	0.10										Start Run 15.5 @ 5200
62115												end of Run
62303												Start Run 16.1 @ 4000'
62400	390	0.10										end of Run
62600	350	0.10										Start Run 16.2 @ 2500
62711												end of Run
62841												Start Run 16.3 @ 1000'
62900	1500	0.11										end of Run
62954												Start Run 17.1 @ 100'
63133												end of Run
63200	570	0.10										Start Run 17.2 @ 1000
63244												end of Run
63301												Start Run 17.3 @ 2500
63600	1195	0.13										end of Run
63645												Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'
63904												end of Run
64000	1150	0.12										Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'
64017												end of Run
64154												Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'
64200	1080											end of Run
64330												Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'
64553												end of Run
64600	1720	0.11										Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'
64708												end of Run
64840												Start Run 17.4 @ 4000'

DATE	RAV 97	MRF TI	01	NAVIGATOR				Fit Lt 'SIMMO' Simpson		
								VOR 1 PT/TAC 1 LTN		
AIRFIELD	TERRACE LTN			COT 1016				VOR 2 - TAC 2		
ATIS	R/W		°C	QNH	1019			ADF LA		
	W/V	210		QFE	102					
	Wx			RPS				Rte Salt 2800		
	Cloud			LFP	6312			MSFL 30		
ATC:	A.	6312		SSR:				INS NAV 09582		
AB	1018	S/H	1020	F/T	8:00					
				ETA	1820					
Time	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT	QNH	LAT/LONG	RUN
103440	069	2P	219	180	213	190 10	FL100	1013	N 5153'0W 00164.5	R1
1105500	086	3P	226	-	-	200 14	-	-	5226.2 W 00005.0	ER1
110800	092	3P	220	-	-	190 08	-	-	N 5233'5E 00127.9	P1
111900	065	2P	178	-	190	105 07	250	1022	5241.7 00224.7	EPI
112540	066	φ	-	-	-	090 09	400	-	5250.0 00254.7	R2 P2
112920	-	-	-	-	-	080 10	-	-	5255.0 00310.6	
113024	-	-	-	-	-	095 08	1000	-	5255.7 00315.5	R2.2
113252	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5259.0 00326.5	E1
115800	069	φ	199	✓	-	120 03	5000	-	5310.4 00325.7	P3
121635	061	1P	175	-	-	125 06	4000	1022	5337.9 00457.8	R4.1
122005	067	1P	185	-	-	150 09	1000'	-	5341.5 00510.1	R4.2
122635	-	-	200	-	-	180 17	3500	-	5350.7 00540.9	R4.3
122855	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5354.0 00582.4	E
122921	072	3P	205	-	-	180 18	4000	-	5354.5 00555.4	R4.4
123220	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5358.3 00610.8	E
123315	07-	-	209	-	-	180 14	5000	-	5359.3 00615.8	R4.5
123850	-	-	198	-	-	170 11	-	-	5406.0 00645.6	E
123943	-	-	-	-	-	-	4000	-	5406.9 00650.5	R5.1
124235	-	-	192	-	-	-	3500	-	5410.3 00705.8	R5.2
124817	-	-	194	-	-	165 11	1000	-	5416.8 00735.5	R5.3
125335	-	-	185	-	-	180 08	1000'	1024	5422.9 00801.8	R6.1
125611	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5426.0 00815.1	E
131207	248	2S	197	-	-	195 04	5200	1021	5516.8 00742.3	P6
131917	240	-	196	-	-	065 03	1000'	-	5507.2 00706.6	R7.1
132428	245	-	185	-	-	195 07	1000'	-	5500.6 00641.6	R7.2
132953	249	-	-	-	-	205 08	3500	-	5454.4 00613.5	R7.3
133200	-	-	193	-	-	210 07	4000'	-	5452.1 00602.4	E ✓
133448	-	-	-	-	-	220 08	-	-	5448.8 00548.2	ER7.4
133550	-	-	187	-	-	220 10	6200	-	5447.6 00543.0	R7.5
134010	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5442.1 00520.5	E
134422	-	-	-	-	-	-	4000	-	5440.6 00514.6	RE.1
134258	-	-	-	-	-	210.10	-	-	5438.8 00507.0	E.
134325	-	-	-	-	-	205 11	-	-	5437.8 00502.2	8.2
ATIS	R/W		°C	QNH			LND			
	W/V			QFE			AB			
	Wx						Time			
	Cloud								CFWD	

4000
5000

6500

DATE		MRF TI		01			NAVIGATOR			Fit Lt 'SIMMO' Simpson		
AIRFIELD	TENERIFE									VOR 1	TAC 1	
										VOR 2	TAC 2	
ATIS		R/W		°C		QNH				ADF		
	z	W/V				QFE						
		Wx				RPS				Rte Salt		
		Cloud				LFP				MSFL		
ATC:						SSR:						
A/B		S/H		F/T								
				ETA								
Time	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT	QNH		LAT/LONG		RUN
										N	W	
ATIS		R/W		°C		QNH				LND		
	z	W/V				QFE				A/B		
		Wx								Time		
		Cloud										
										CFWD		

300MB
HEIGHT DM.

GMTAIN T+ 24

VT 00Z MON 18/ 8/97 TUES 19/ 8/97

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:37.42
CHART 27
PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

FS/FUXX EGRR

Printed from V. 4.17-1.92 31/04/1991 11:08 AM 07

Met. Office, Canada, D.O. (form A) 1981 [Amended May 1982]

Printed from V. 4.17-1.92 31/04/1991 11:08 AM 07

FS/FUXX EGRR

T+48 VT 00Z WED 20 AUG 1997

POL. STER. PROJ. STAND. PARALLEL 60°N

SEA LEVEL ISOPLETHS
1000-500 mb THICKNESS ISOPLETHS

Printed and drawn in the Cartographic Section, Met. Office, Exeter, Devon, PL11 3BA, United Kingdom

T+72 VT 00Z THU 21 AUG 1997

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 19 AUG 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 18 AUG 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28 **

** TOTAL PAGE .001 **
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE.001

18 AUG '97 03:42

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Section, METD/18, Bracknell, MLE/Cartography from METD/18
Meteo Plot by the Cartographic Section, METD/18, Bracknell, MLE/Cartography from METD/18

500-1000MB
5000MB

- THICKNESS DM.
- - - HEIGHT DM.

I+ 0

GRAIN

18/ 8/97

MON

18/ 8/97

VT 00Z

MON

18/ 8/97

MON

18/ 8/97

MON

18/ 8/97

MON

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.43.46 CHART 13 [PHEA50 EGRR 0000Z

500-1000MB
500MB

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

T + 24
GMAIN

18/ 8/97 VT 00Z TUES 19/ 8/97

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.43.58 CHART 13 PHEE50_EGRR_0000Z

18 AUG '97 03:38

FACIT 4-UP

00Z 18 AUG 1997

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 23Z

10	275	8
15	295	16
20	305	28
25	300	21
30	305	10
40	245	10
50	225	2
60	260	7
70	240	9
85	235	9
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 196 -63
305 29

10	1652	
15	1393	
20	1211	
25	1069	
30	948	
40	748	
50	500	
60	314	
85	174	
100	17	

MAX MIL
TROP 196 -63
305 29

HERSBY
03496
AT 23Z

10	305	4
15	280	11
20	240	18
25	290	19
30	270	12
40	274	12
50	255	5
60	205	7
70	235	10
85	CALM	
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 204 -62
230 15

10	1651	
15	1390	
20	1205	
25	1066	
30	947	
40	747	
50	478	
60	316	
70	196	
85	17	
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 204 -62
230 15

HERSTHONCEUX
03882
AT 23Z

10	285	12
15	285	11
20	280	17
25	305	18
30	285	13
40	335	12
50	285	9
60	245	11
70	235	9
85	175	9
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 201 -61
270 14

10	1653	
15	1392	
20	1209	
25	1067	
30	947	
40	745	
50	579	
60	316	
85	156	
100	16	

MAX MIL
TROP 201 -61
270 14

ABERFORTH
03502
AT 23Z

10	285	30
15	295	24
20	280	17
25	340	19
30	280	19
40	275	15
50	265	11
60	265	6
70	265	6
85	165	15
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 197 -62
290 28

10	1208	
15	1067	
20	946	
25	745	
30	579	
40	314	
50	154	
70	154	
85	17	
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 197 -62
290 28

10	161.0	
15	121.0	
20	201.0	
25	166.0	
30	265.2	
40	297.3	
50	137.3	
60	562.5	
70		
85		
100		

MAX MIL
TROP 197 -62
290 28

11T 00Z MON 18/ 8/ 97 LMAIN

11T 00Z MON 18/ 8/ 97 1. 0 - - SNOW PROBABILITY %
 HSL PRESSURE hPa

11T 00Z MON 18/ 8/ 97 T. 0 H.S.P. TEMP. 020 C. 950MB
 METEOROLOGICAL CHART AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 02-24-96 CHARTS26

OPCA98 ECRR 0000Z

U:10-05 A:10-05 C:12-05 E:13-05 F:15-05 G:16-05 H:17-05 J:18-05 K:19-05 L:20-05 M:22-05 N:23-05 O:24-05 P:25-05 Q:26-05 R:25-29 S:30-34 T:35-39 U:40-44 V:45-49 W:50-54 X:55-59 Y:60-64 Z:65 AND OVER

Header file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A571_RAW_HDDR.DAT;
Data file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A571_RAW_DATA.DAT; 72.3 Mbytes (148030 blocks
)

Transcription on 18-AUG-97 20:59:24
Extraction on 18-AUG-97 20:59:24

Data set type 2

ISS 31 DBF 31 IC 02 121 parameters recorded 889 samples per second

7 sections of data

Section	Starts					Ends				
	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC
1	07:48:23	028103	000	00011	00001	08:29:21	030561	007	02469	02459
2	08:29:24	030564	007	02472	02460	08:41:51	031311	008	03219	03207
3	08:41:55	031315	008	03223	03208	14:32:24	052344	090	24252	24237
4	14:36:06	052566	090	24474	24238	15:01:48	054108	105	26016	25780
5	15:01:51	054111	105	26019	25781	15:14:12	054852	112	26760	26522
6	15:14:15	054855	112	26763	26523	15:25:11	055511	117	27419	27179
7	15:25:14	055514	118	27422	27180	18:09:01	065341	173	37249	37007

A571

GPS data
07:50:44 - 18:12:36

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: *AS71*

DATE: *18/8/97*

MRF *1* *JACIA*

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	✓	✓	
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
LOWER CLEAR	✓	✓	
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	✓	X	
CLOUD PHYSICS	✓	✓	
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	✓	✓	

- ① TORQUE ON A055 = 4.0
- ② SLIGHT ECCENTRIC ON A0A SHAFT
- ③ A/C SCIENTISTS DISPLAY LOSING VERTICAL HOLD
- ④ FR DISPLAY BUNDLED OUT UNABLE TO RECOVER
- ⑤ TWE NEEDS NEW CONSTANTS
- ⑥ DRS TIME REPEATER IN REAR VAN U/S
- ⑦ ROTARY SWITCH ON FL CANNONS NOT VERY LOOSE

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEEMOS log ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEEMOS log Chemistry log <i>PAN GC, bottles, PERCH ETC. NOT GIVEN TO FLIGHT LEADER</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instrument status forms RTD prints — <i>NOT GIVEN TO FLIGHT LEADER</i> Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

TRAJ_A970818.TXT

From 0Z 17/ 8/1997 to 12Z 18/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970818 (2D Model levels)

From 12Z 15/ 8/1997 to 12Z 18/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970818 (2D Model levels)

From 12Z 15/ 8/1997 to 15Z 18/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970818 (2D Model levels)

From 15Z 15/ 8/1997 to 18Z 18/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A571 18-AUG-97

P5 5000'-50'(123850-125615) + p5up 50'-5200'(125615-131207)

A571 18-AUG-97

P8 5200'-50'(134012-135150) + P9 50'-5300'(135150-141655)

A571 18-AUG-97

P10 5300'-50'(144135-145307) + P11 50'-5300'(145513-151222)

A571 18-AUG-97

P12 5300'-50'(151222-152737) + P13 50'-5300'(152737-154353)

A571 18-AUG-97

P14 5300'-50'(155740-160903) + P15 50'-5300'(161121-162710)

A571 18-AUG-97

P16 5300'-50'(162710-163853) + P17 50'-FL110(163853-170335)

A571 18-AUG-97 R1 FL100 From 103441-105500 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:39

A571 18-AUG-97 R1 FL100 From 103441-105500 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 13:51

A571 18-AUG-97 R1 FL100 From 103441-105500 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:39

A571 18-AUG-97 R1 FL100 From 103441-105500 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:39

A571 18-AUG-97 R1 FL100 From 103441-105500 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:13

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 699.963
 Standard dev 0.253849
 Max value 700.685
 Min value 699.181

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 276.391
 Standard dev 0.713303
 Max value 277.440
 Min value 275.034

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 263.110
 Standard dev 3.45029
 Max value 271.664
 Min value 254.393

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 49.0401
 Standard dev 5.08286
 Max value 65.2713
 Min value 36.7189

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 11.2521
 Standard dev 4.36051
 Max value 37.0144
 Min value 2.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 0.000000
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 0.000000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 3012.55
 Standard dev 2.85096
 Max value 3021.33
 Min value 3004.44

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 52.2143
 Standard dev 0.151539
 Max value 52.4386
 Min value 51.9186

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean -1.01726
 Standard dev 0.529853
 Max value -7.770211e-02
 Min value -1.90425

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 6.69482
 Standard dev 0.500366
 Max value 7.90555
 Min value 5.21112

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 0.988623
 Standard dev 0.520570
 Max value 2.71572
 Min value -0.203735

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 0.205332
 Standard dev 0.248235
 Max value 0.890930
 Min value -0.881760

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 6.78899
 Standard dev 0.478205
 Max value 7.92373
 Min value 5.35968

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 188.400

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1220
 Mean 110.224
 Standard dev 1.60676
 Max value 113.321
 Min value 106.613

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 65.1450

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:42

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 13:54

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:42

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 13:54

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P1 From 110801-111859 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:16

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 659
Mean 869.038
Standard dev 97.6533
Max value 1016.23
Min value 698.604

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 659
Mean 286.287
Standard dev 5.94477
Max value 294.048
Min value 274.764

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 659
Mean 279.286
Standard dev 5.70753
Max value 291.000
Min value 269.108

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 659
Mean 58.4580
Standard dev 14.4357
Max value 80.1339
Min value 24.7610

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 659
Mean 765.442
Standard dev 601.645
Max value 2096.86
Min value 60.0429

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 659
Mean 1.38996
Standard dev 14.5423
Max value 212.194
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 659
Mean 1318.78
Standard dev 931.452
Max value 3027.82
Min value -24.7417

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 659
Mean 52.6016
Standard dev 4.237010e-02
Max value 52.6967
Min value 52.5603

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 659
Mean 1.97391
Standard dev 0.274005
Max value 2.41874
Min value 1.47477

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 659
Mean 2.11940
Standard dev 0.993278
Max value 4.94238
Min value 0.267349

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 659
Mean -1.17652
Standard dev 1.85290
Max value 2.31503
Min value -4.88535

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 659
Mean 1.20167
Standard dev 0.556809
Max value 1.89835
Min value -0.210388

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 659
Mean 2.95363
Standard dev 1.25205
Max value 5.57911
Min value 0.535712

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 150.965

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 659
Mean 102.077
Standard dev 4.80223
Max value 112.019
Min value 93.5498

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 76.6338

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:50

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:50

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:24

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:50

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:50

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:51

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:24

A571 18-AUG-97 P2 350'-5000' From 112540-115344 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:03

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1685
Mean 926.370
Standard dev 53.2469
Max value 1010.92
Min value 851.966

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1685
Mean 290.525
Standard dev 2.18739
Max value 294.065
Min value 286.645

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1685
Mean 279.515
Standard dev 7.22936
Max value 292.133
Min value 269.405

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1685
Mean 48.1627
Standard dev 17.5921
Max value 92.7402
Min value 32.3334

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1685
Mean 551.337
Standard dev 644.878
Max value 2111.66
Min value 36.0152

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1685
Mean 0.379451
Standard dev 6.65335
Max value 180.473
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1685
Mean 865.302
Standard dev 487.154
Max value 1522.15
Min value 101.123

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1685
Mean 53.0351
Standard dev 8.993831e-02
Max value 53.1696
Min value 52.8362

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1685
Mean 3.37412
Standard dev 0.236123
Max value 3.82296
Min value 2.91770

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1685
Mean 0.634004
Standard dev 0.984894
Max value 2.85158
Min value -0.853027

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1685
Mean -2.20381
Standard dev 1.66889
Max value 1.22388
Min value -5.05322

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1685
Mean -3.323244e-02
Standard dev 0.350795
Max value 0.687050
Min value -1.36459

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1685
Mean 2.64806
Standard dev 1.41445
Max value 5.05662
Min value 0.163421

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 106.050

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1685
Mean 97.0114
Standard dev 4.18398
Max value 106.284
Min value 90.0117

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 38.1531

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:55

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:56

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:30

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:56

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:56

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 08:56

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:30

A571 18-AUG-97 P3 5000'-400' From 115759-121633 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:09

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1115
Mean 927.752
Standard dev 44.2715
Max value 1010.18
Min value 853.722

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1115
Mean 291.333
Standard dev 2.44817
Max value 295.275
Min value 286.981

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1115
Mean 277.682
Standard dev 8.23712
Max value 291.755
Min value 261.947

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1115
Mean 60.5759
Standard dev 18.2925
Max value 89.5803
Min value 34.4561

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1115
Mean 708.992
Standard dev 681.750
Max value 2217.12
Min value 17.0028

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1115
Mean 1.432007e-02
Standard dev 4.163528e-02
Max value 0.235637
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1115
Mean 855.849
Standard dev 408.611
Max value 1522.15
Min value 105.956

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1115
Mean 53.3969
Standard dev 0.127307
Max value 53.6090
Min value 53.1761

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1115
Mean 4.18091
Standard dev 0.426971
Max value 4.91127
Min value 3.43598

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1115
Mean 3.56873
Standard dev 1.62648
Max value 6.95856
Min value -0.104645

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1115
Mean -2.51224
Standard dev 0.441924
Max value -0.976784
Min value -4.14415

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1115
Mean 0.378182
Standard dev 0.229270
Max value 1.02708
Min value -0.116638

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1115
Mean 4.49727
Standard dev 1.28896
Max value 7.28846
Min value 1.70607

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 144.856

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1115
Mean 98.6613
Standard dev 2.48445
Max value 103.432
Min value 92.8892

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 63.8583

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:02

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:02

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:37

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P4 400'-5000' From 121633-123850 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 14:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 921.738
 Standard dev 57.4755
 Max value 1010.18
 Min value 852.438

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 290.794
 Standard dev 4.08485
 Max value 296.157
 Min value 285.617

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 284.292
 Standard dev 2.60757
 Max value 291.755
 Min value 281.484

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 69.3189
 Standard dev 9.20859
 Max value 85.1277
 Min value 58.1888

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 1241.66
 Standard dev 254.777
 Max value 2107.12
 Min value 93.7137

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 2.256708e-02
 Standard dev 4.798769e-02
 Max value 0.238163
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 911.088
 Standard dev 527.686
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 105.958

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 53.8663
 Standard dev 0.142787
 Max value 54.1021
 Min value 53.6090

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 5.80359
 Standard dev 0.542170
 Max value 6.76926
 Min value 4.91127

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 5.34040
 Standard dev 2.14721
 Max value 8.39075
 Min value -0.192146

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1338
 Mean -0.848773
 Standard dev 1.11236
 Max value 0.755646
 Min value -4.10670

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1338
 Mean -8.753458e-02
 Standard dev 0.289924
 Max value 0.645531
 Min value -1.12927

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 5.67213
 Standard dev 1.70671
 Max value 8.39665
 Min value 2.34079

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 170.969

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1338
 Mean 98.8957
 Standard dev 3.56614
 Max value 105.567
 Min value 84.7133

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 65.8239

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:22

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:22

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:08

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P5 5000'-50' From 123850-125615 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:22

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1046
Mean 955.594
Standard dev 54.3344
Max value 1021.34
Min value 854.600

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1046
Mean 293.335
Standard dev 3.53810
Max value 297.479
Min value 285.838

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1046
Mean 285.285
Standard dev 3.81915
Max value 292.583
Min value 281.404

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1046
Mean 58.9700
Standard dev 9.95263
Max value 80.5293
Min value 34.8313

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1046
Mean 1664.58
Standard dev 399.976
Max value 5929.08
Min value 622.082

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1046
Mean 3.183531e-02
Standard dev 5.541008e-02
Max value 0.238170
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1046
Mean 609.877
Standard dev 496.988
Max value 1522.15
Min value 15.2598

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1046
Mean 54.2677
Standard dev 9.715140e-02
Max value 54.4351
Min value 54.1021

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1046
Mean 7.52507
Standard dev 0.430604
Max value 8.25605
Min value 6.76926

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1046
Mean 4.92102
Standard dev 0.783479
Max value 6.60842
Min value 3.46097

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1046
Mean -0.653889
Standard dev 0.809699
Max value 0.721931
Min value -3.90214

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1046
Mean 0.478022
Standard dev 0.228834
Max value 1.03766
Min value -1.724243e-03

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1046
Mean 5.03974
Standard dev 0.716798
Max value 6.61675
Min value 3.74856

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 172.431

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1046
Mean 97.9823
Standard dev 2.70001
Max value 102.526
Min value 92.4635

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 69.0608

A571 18-AUG-97 p5up 50'-5200' From 125615-131207 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:14

A571 18-AUG-97 p5up 50'-5200' From 125615-131207 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:28

A571 18-AUG-97 p5up 50'-5200' From 125615-131207 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:14

A571 18-AUG-97 p5up 50'-5200' From 125615-131207 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:14

A571 18-AUG-97 P6 5200'-50' From 131207-131847 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:17

A571 18-AUG-97 P6 5200'-50' From 131207-131847 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:17

A571 18-AUG-97 P6 5200'-50' From 131207-131847 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:17

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:23

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:38

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:23

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:23

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A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:23

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:38

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:23

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:24

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:24

A571 18-AUG-97 P7 50'-5200' From 131847-134012 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:38

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1286
Mean 932.944
Standard dev 66.4617
Max value 1021.56
Min value 846.146

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1286
Mean 291.010
Standard dev 4.16930
Max value 295.627
Min value 284.844

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1286
Mean 285.366
Standard dev 4.76898
Max value 293.548
Min value 273.167

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1286
Mean 73.6261
Standard dev 7.76434
Max value 84.9424
Min value 56.0856

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1286
Mean 1221.97
Standard dev 494.857
Max value 2628.87
Min value 79.2886

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1286
Mean 4.535018e-02
Standard dev 7.484096e-02
Max value 0.238178
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1021
Mean 608.686
Standard dev 509.289
Max value 1522.15
Min value 14.1447

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1286
Mean 54.9139
Standard dev 0.120337
Max value 55.1347
Min value 54.7011

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1286
Mean 6.25194
Standard dev 0.526864
Max value 7.14976
Min value 5.34293

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1286
Mean 2.36080
Standard dev 1.54397
Max value 4.38084
Min value -0.652184

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1286
Mean 0.678285
Standard dev 1.55217
Max value 3.10818
Min value -2.11758

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1286
Mean -0.147496
Standard dev 0.390283
Max value 1.12774
Min value -1.09297

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1286
Mean 3.01516
Standard dev 1.31642
Max value 5.32220
Min value 9.361210e-02

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 196.030

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1286
Mean 99.0725
Standard dev 2.77769
Max value 103.651
Min value 92.4818

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 247.373

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

A571 18-AUG-97 P8 5200'-50' From 134012-135150 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:28

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 699
Mean 938.640
Standard dev 50.4803
Max value 1021.46
Min value 846.910

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 699
Mean 290.696
Standard dev 2.43286
Max value 294.246
Min value 285.555

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 699
Mean 285.036
Standard dev 5.34484
Max value 292.439
Min value 271.800

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 699
Mean 70.6960
Standard dev 8.68804
Max value 87.6796
Min value 53.9484

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 699
Mean 1060.53
Standard dev 351.203
Max value 1837.18
Min value 181.413

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 699
Mean 9.162335e-02
Standard dev 0.117397
Max value 0.476372
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 693
Mean 754.499
Standard dev 457.757
Max value 1522.15
Min value 15.0739

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 699
Mean 54.5852
Standard dev 6.920141e-02
Max value 54.7011
Min value 54.4613

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 699
Mean 4.85817
Standard dev 0.282377
Max value 5.34293
Min value 4.36772

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 699
Mean 0.620869
Standard dev 3.86928
Max value 5.05405
Min value -5.12530

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 699
Mean -2.326223e-02
Standard dev 1.94312
Max value 3.50170
Min value -3.21188

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 699
Mean 0.653829
Standard dev 0.224385
Max value 1.21224
Min value -0.140137

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 699
Mean 4.17833
Standard dev 1.28457
Max value 5.69370
Min value 0.158629

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 177.854

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 699
Mean 98.0674
Standard dev 2.01647
Max value 101.474
Min value 92.6068

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 247.038

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:51

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:43

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 14:51

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:44

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:44

A571 18-AUG-97 P9 50'-5300' From 135150-141655 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:10

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 906.179
 Standard dev 55.3748
 Max value 1021.49
 Min value 841.821

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 289.419
 Standard dev 2.69121
 Max value 294.259
 Min value 285.475

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 277.249
 Standard dev 7.66829
 Max value 292.551
 Min value 262.976

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 50.5714
 Standard dev 15.5667
 Max value 80.8987
 Min value 27.5023

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 346.361
 Standard dev 411.089
 Max value 1409.13
 Min value 10.0010

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 1.969061e-02
 Standard dev 5.624673e-02
 Max value 0.466327
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 944.166
 Standard dev 495.584
 Max value 1536.07
 Min value -68.3368

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 54.0747
 Standard dev 0.220884
 Max value 54.4613
 Min value 53.7551

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 3.40959
 Standard dev 0.560931
 Max value 4.36772
 Min value 2.36998

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1506
 Mean -1.95944
 Standard dev 1.00632
 Max value -0.528160
 Min value -5.01066

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1506
 Mean -2.12746
 Standard dev 0.846104
 Max value 0.748901
 Min value -3.79613

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1506
 Mean -0.133962
 Standard dev 0.423995
 Max value 0.892494
 Min value -1.53027

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 3.02290
 Standard dev 0.977576
 Max value 5.45474
 Min value 1.13579

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 47.3542

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1506
 Mean 99.7728
 Standard dev 2.62634
 Max value 105.948
 Min value 94.3568

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 239.000

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:54

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:01

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:54

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:54

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:15

A571 18-AUG-97 transit 5300' From 141655-144135 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:01

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1260
Mean 844.618
Standard dev 1.21733
Max value 846.089
Min value 840.504

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1260
Mean 285.140
Standard dev 0.456561
Max value 286.175
Min value 284.290

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1260
Mean 280.822
Standard dev 2.72566
Max value 283.831
Min value 272.982

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1260
Mean 66.6094
Standard dev 14.2419
Max value 93.8742
Min value 30.1451

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1260
Mean 725.622
Standard dev 369.346
Max value 1784.04
Min value 9.00058

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1260
Mean 2.314857e-02
Standard dev 4.952032e-02
Max value 0.297333
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1260
Mean 1509.06
Standard dev 11.7483
Max value 1548.82
Min value 1494.88

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1260
Mean 54.0676
Standard dev 0.211583
Max value 54.4384
Min value 53.7524

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1260
Mean 1.34733
Standard dev 0.499512
Max value 2.36998
Min value 0.561730

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1260
Mean 2.53551
Standard dev 2.42194
Max value 6.53325
Min value -1.40319

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1260
Mean -1.16143
Standard dev 1.74480
Max value 1.85281
Min value -4.58744

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1260
Mean -0.108418
Standard dev 0.321389
Max value 1.34117
Min value -0.544594

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1112
Mean 3.87705
Standard dev 1.55579
Max value 6.53811
Min value 1.10734

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 155.389

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1260
Mean 131.812
Standard dev 22.7976
Max value 153.634
Min value 98.3530

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 308.163

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:03

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:57

A571 18-AUG-97 P10 5300'-50' From 144135-145307 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:03

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 693
Mean 915.508
Standard dev 49.6679
Max value 989.174
Min value 842.902

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 693
Mean 289.061
Standard dev 2.76999
Max value 293.128
Min value 284.460

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 693
Mean 283.873
Standard dev 1.84784
Max value 286.419
Min value 279.842

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 693
Mean 75.1514
Standard dev 5.12337
Max value 84.7107
Min value 58.7489

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 693
Mean 1325.88
Standard dev 362.631
Max value 2875.16
Min value 412.648

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 693
Mean 3.330284e-02
Standard dev 5.901698e-02
Max value 0.235629
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 693
Mean 857.233
Standard dev 449.460
Max value 1525.62
Min value 202.365

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 693
Mean 54.5704
Standard dev 7.171755e-02
Max value 54.6889
Min value 54.4384

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 693
Mean 1.91006
Standard dev 0.281131
Max value 2.39071
Min value 1.42086

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 693
Mean 3.26909
Standard dev 0.983069
Max value 5.64710
Min value 1.55567

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 693
Mean -1.41858
Standard dev 0.701856
Max value 0.132721
Min value -3.10457

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 693
Mean 0.615584
Standard dev 0.302371
Max value 1.27274
Min value -1.439667e-02

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 693
Mean 3.68047
Standard dev 0.781852
Max value 5.65920
Min value 2.36771

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 156.542

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 693
Mean 99.0573
Standard dev 2.76107
Max value 104.590
Min value 93.2097

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 66.0418

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:59

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:06

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:59

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:19

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:59

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:06

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:59

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 09:59

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:19

A571 18-AUG-97 P11 50'-5300' From 145513-151222 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:06

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1028
Mean 934.557
Standard dev 56.9489
Max value 1021.69
Min value 841.350

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1028
Mean 289.807
Standard dev 2.69454
Max value 293.409
Min value 284.632

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1028
Mean 283.811
Standard dev 4.87438
Max value 292.318
Min value 273.239

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1028
Mean 63.1445
Standard dev 10.6978
Max value 89.2632
Min value 34.1863

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1028
Mean 845.787
Standard dev 347.406
Max value 1657.56
Min value 41.8583

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1028
Mean 5.086089e-02
Standard dev 0.109205
Max value 0.699605
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1028
Mean 689.232
Standard dev 508.712
Max value 1540.63
Min value -70.0172

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1028
Mean 54.9796
Standard dev 0.143339
Max value 55.2052
Min value 54.7356

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1028
Mean 3.17990
Standard dev 0.372036
Max value 3.86500
Min value 2.55068

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1028
Mean 0.580737
Standard dev 0.474172
Max value 2.04143
Min value -0.349823

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1028
Mean -1.65483
Standard dev 1.15122
Max value 0.823250
Min value -3.47692

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1028
Mean -0.189541
Standard dev 0.305502
Max value 0.554306
Min value -0.748734

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1028
Mean 1.93805
Standard dev 0.932296
Max value 3.77781
Min value 3.978547e-02

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 109.338

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1028
Mean 97.7552
Standard dev 3.81927
Max value 105.633
Min value 89.0942

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 58.1646

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:09

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:05

A571 18-AUG-97 P12 5300'-50' From 151222-152737 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:09

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 912
Mean 941.353
Standard dev 50.5663
Max value 1021.42
Min value 843.097

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 912
Mean 290.377
Standard dev 2.75048
Max value 294.451
Min value 284.960

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 912
Mean 284.691
Standard dev 5.19103
Max value 292.755
Min value 268.867

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 912
Mean 69.0309
Standard dev 5.93715
Max value 78.1899
Min value 39.9938

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 912
Mean 1050.68
Standard dev 363.191
Max value 5471.72
Min value 117.447

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 912
Mean 4.637232e-02
Standard dev 8.775266e-02
Max value 0.486841
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 912
Mean 626.212
Standard dev 448.796
Max value 1523.74
Min value -67.7991

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 912
Mean 55.3653
Standard dev 8.833746e-02
Max value 55.5091
Min value 55.2052

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 912
Mean 4.51592
Standard dev 0.367300
Max value 5.14267
Min value 3.86500

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 912
Mean 0.118028
Standard dev 1.19104
Max value 2.49294
Min value -1.86889

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 912
Mean -2.01038
Standard dev 1.30728
Max value 0.286713
Min value -4.13973

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 912
Mean 0.546569
Standard dev 0.281189
Max value 1.18470
Min value -0.297203

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 912
Mean 2.52143
Standard dev 0.907190
Max value 4.22927
Min value 4.575512e-02

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 93.3599

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 912
Mean 97.6471
Standard dev 3.16323
Max value 104.950
Min value 91.2097

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 67.3438

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:11

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:13

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:11

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:25

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:11

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:13

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:11

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:11

A571 18-AUG-97 P13 50'-5300' From 152737-154353 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:25

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 948.704
 Standard dev 65.3702
 Max value 1021.22
 Min value 839.943

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 290.920
 Standard dev 3.41401
 Max value 294.442
 Min value 284.527

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 287.459
 Standard dev 3.89714
 Max value 292.755
 Min value 281.460

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 71.6586
 Standard dev 9.01758
 Max value 86.8440
 Min value 56.7514

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 1052.17
 Standard dev 228.229
 Max value 1854.21
 Min value 269.646

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 7.184496e-02
 Standard dev 9.646642e-02
 Max value 0.481549
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 568.001
 Standard dev 581.328
 Max value 1554.25
 Min value -66.1161

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 55.6596
 Standard dev 9.163661e-02
 Max value 55.8284
 Min value 55.5091

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 5.81713
 Standard dev 0.397957
 Max value 6.52951
 Min value 5.14267

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 1.14271
 Standard dev 2.65740
 Max value 6.36284
 Min value -1.87668

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 977
 Mean -1.05194
 Standard dev 2.19334
 Max value 2.21338
 Min value -4.27561

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 977
 Mean -0.286943
 Standard dev 0.367261
 Max value 0.698723
 Min value -1.14994

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 3.53017
 Standard dev 1.34627
 Max value 6.68637
 Min value 0.955130

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 137.368

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 977
 Mean 96.9947
 Standard dev 3.36546
 Max value 111.036
 Min value 90.4234

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 67.8508

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:15

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:15

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:15

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:16

A571 18-AUG-97 P14 5300'-50' From 155740-160903 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:15

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 684
Mean 915.407
Standard dev 49.6639
Max value 987.589
Min value 841.455

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 684
Mean 288.706
Standard dev 2.43956
Max value 292.423
Min value 285.518

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 684
Mean 277.904
Standard dev 8.07055
Max value 288.372
Min value 260.107

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 684
Mean 61.4114
Standard dev 8.04181
Max value 80.0904
Min value 45.2525

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 684
Mean 615.785
Standard dev 340.029
Max value 1387.94
Min value 35.0490

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 684
Mean 2.054192e-02
Standard dev 4.490712e-02
Max value 0.238155
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 684
Mean 858.157
Standard dev 449.738
Max value 1539.61
Min value 215.832

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 684
Mean 56.6416
Standard dev 6.878541e-02
Max value 56.7597
Min value 56.5237

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 684
Mean 5.85347
Standard dev 0.294086
Max value 6.36565
Min value 5.34903

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 684
Mean -1.25889
Standard dev 1.79545
Max value 1.77423
Min value -3.98997

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 684
Mean 0.134714
Standard dev 1.11853
Max value 2.13965
Min value -2.71233

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 684
Mean 0.465516
Standard dev 0.244044
Max value 1.05924
Min value -0.143791

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 684
Mean 2.23722
Standard dev 1.03323
Max value 4.13962
Min value 0.199022

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 353.892

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 684
Mean 98.5796
Standard dev 3.14669
Max value 103.516
Min value 92.2995

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 247.146

A571 18--AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:21

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:18

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:21

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:33

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:22

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:18

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:22

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:22

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:33

A571 18-AUG-97 P15 50'-5300' From 161121-162710 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:18

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 950
Mean 919.199
Standard dev 64.2354
Max value 1021.45
Min value 841.032

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 950
Mean 288.598
Standard dev 3.32771
Max value 293.964
Min value 284.121

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 950
Mean 282.014
Standard dev 4.58615
Max value 290.502
Min value 268.899

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 950
Mean 58.1474
Standard dev 8.27402
Max value 73.4518
Min value 35.2021

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 950
Mean 559.737
Standard dev 212.803
Max value 1154.65
Min value 60.1196

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 950
Mean 1.286314e-02
Standard dev 3.411238e-02
Max value 0.246101
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 950
Mean 830.351
Standard dev 576.739
Max value 1543.70
Min value -68.0007

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 950
Mean 56.3078
Standard dev 9.854469e-02
Max value 56.4753
Min value 56.1278

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 950
Mean 4.45419
Standard dev 0.404708
Max value 5.14862
Min value 3.75288

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean -1.32834
Standard dev 1.12054
Max value 0.299034
Min value -3.91546

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean -0.636067
Standard dev 1.33267
Max value 1.45302
Min value -3.45467

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean -0.266670
Standard dev 0.358512
Max value 0.826767
Min value -0.958702

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 2.08594
Standard dev 1.19129
Max value 4.19513
Min value 0.239424

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 22.5962

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 98.4734
Standard dev 4.06153
Max value 108.477
Min value 88.7776

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 245.860

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:21

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:21

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:26

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:27

A571 18-AUG-97 P16 5300'-50' From 162710-163853 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:21

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 704
Mean 942.368
Standard dev 51.2701
Max value 1021.62
Min value 841.041

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 704
Mean 289.559
Standard dev 2.72136
Max value 293.829
Min value 284.549

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 704
Mean 284.568
Standard dev 3.00191
Max value 290.928
Min value 279.202

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 704
Mean 66.8358
Standard dev 9.93216
Max value 93.1399
Min value 48.8321

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 704
Mean 1137.43
Standard dev 474.351
Max value 2757.67
Min value 131.995

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 704
Mean 4.503517e-02
Standard dev 6.972039e-02
Max value 0.246101
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 704
Mean 617.534
Standard dev 455.640
Max value 1543.62
Min value -69.4122

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 704
Mean 55.9763
Standard dev 9.169526e-02
Max value 56.1278
Min value 55.8062

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 704
Mean 3.26383
Standard dev 0.275041
Max value 3.75288
Min value 2.81046

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 704
Mean -0.551443
Standard dev 0.490254
Max value 0.489861
Min value -1.86092

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 704
Mean -0.850417
Standard dev 1.01562
Max value 1.68878
Min value -3.18888

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 704
Mean 0.613619
Standard dev 0.283091
Max value 1.26933
Min value -5.655670e-02

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 704
Mean 1.37880
Standard dev 0.629906
Max value 3.18898
Min value 0.314703

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 57.0391

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 704
Mean 97.2720
Standard dev 2.92527
Max value 102.686
Min value 89.5209

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 238.653

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'--FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:34

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:25

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:34

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:40

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:34

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:25

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:34

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:34

A571 18-AUG-97 P17 50'-FL110 From 163853-170335 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 15:40

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 870.891
 Standard dev 95.2057
 Max value 1021.54
 Min value 670.485

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 285.595
 Standard dev 5.57674
 Max value 293.812
 Min value 272.857

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 282.077
 Standard dev 5.69450
 Max value 291.442
 Min value 259.745

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 71.3348
 Standard dev 12.9575
 Max value 94.1206
 Min value 43.1556

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 897.298
 Standard dev 495.387
 Max value 2586.77
 Min value 10.4206

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 6.81120
 Standard dev 37.6765
 Max value 370.332
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 1299.19
 Standard dev 908.150
 Max value 3349.41
 Min value -68.7401

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 55.4339
 Standard dev 0.205991
 Max value 55.8062
 Min value 55.0539

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 1.86851
 Standard dev 0.559535
 Max value 2.81046
 Min value 0.922822

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 1.14575
 Standard dev 1.04763
 Max value 3.47430
 Min value -0.432373

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 0.231839
 Standard dev 1.88939
 Max value 4.76508
 Min value -3.53215

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1483
 Mean -0.301717
 Standard dev 0.466250
 Max value 0.791191
 Min value -1.83356

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 2.17939
 Standard dev 1.13216
 Max value 4.81985
 Min value 0.141478

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 191.439

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1483
 Mean 100.459
 Standard dev 4.92874
 Max value 110.574
 Min value 89.5598

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 234.948

A571 18-AUG-97 R18 FL110 From 170335-172323 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:37

A571 18-AUG-97 R18 FL110 From 170335-172323 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 15:28

A571 18-AUG-97 R18 FL110 From 170335-172323 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:37

A571 18-AUG-97 R18 FL110 From 170335-172323 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:37

A571 18-AUG-97 R18 FL110 From 170335-172323 Plotted 11-Dec-1997 10:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 671.637
 Standard dev 1.27343
 Max value 675.467
 Min value 667.518

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 273.247
 Standard dev 0.317931
 Max value 273.880
 Min value 272.676

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 264.292
 Standard dev 3.15402
 Max value 271.013
 Min value 252.464

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 54.3713
 Standard dev 4.24780
 Max value 64.7806
 Min value 44.8754

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 73.8935
 Standard dev 60.4059
 Max value 358.096
 Min value 3.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 1.186519e-05
 Standard dev 4.091342e-04
 Max value 1.410772e-02
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 3336.02
 Standard dev 14.7909
 Max value 3383.97
 Min value 3291.65

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 54.3513
 Standard dev 0.443066
 Max value 55.0539
 Min value 53.5663

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 0.343260
 Standard dev 0.272997
 Max value 0.922822
 Min value -6.311616e-02

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 1.03998
 Standard dev 0.715220
 Max value 2.80797
 Min value -0.410583

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 3.07422
 Standard dev 0.747920
 Max value 4.57264
 Min value 1.02821

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 0.308612
 Standard dev 0.376721
 Max value 1.05222
 Min value -1.51495

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 3.33762
 Standard dev 0.680481
 Max value 4.73063
 Min value 1.43431

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 251.310

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1189
 Mean 153.945
 Standard dev 9.01693
 Max value 160.202
 Min value 104.932

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 201.087

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using actual scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO₂) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

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